

ISic2922

Epitaph for Laurentius, a doctor, and his wife Prosdocia

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Arancio hypogeum, villa Landolina

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. † Memoria Laurenti
2. medici et uxor eius
3. Prosdocia

Apparatus

Text of Korhonen 2010

Translation (en)

In memory of Laurentius the doctor and his wife Prosocia

Commentary**Digital identifiers:**

TM 175838

EDR 073823

EDCS 13900570

Bibliography

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